

Screening of Metal Complexes for Biological Activity. Part-III. Copper(II) and Nickel(II) Tungstate Complexes with Ethylenediamine and Propylenediamine

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The study of various transition metal complexes as models for understanding many biochemical process is becoming increasingly important nowadays. In the present communication two complexes of copper(II) and nickel(II) tungstates with ethylenediamine and propylene diamine are reported which are found to possess weak diuretic and anti-inflammatory activities.

Results and Discussion

The complexes (Table 1) have been formulated $[\text{Cu}(\text{am})_2]\text{WO}_4$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{am})_3]\text{WO}_4$, where am =

values (3.00 B.M.) and three transition in spectra, viz. ν_3 , ν_2 and ν_1 around 30.00, 18.50 and 11.90 kK respectively, along with their Dq , B and ν_2/ν_1 values which are 1 100 cm^{-1} , 1 180 cm^{-1} and 1.60 respectively.

All the complexes stimulated central nervous system and their increased spontaneous motor activity (SMA) is probably due to their direct action on the effector cells and the increased rate of respiration is a result of dilation of branchioles and stimulation of respiratory centre. The complexes

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour)	Analysis : Found/(Calcd.)					Λ $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.
	M	C	H	N	WO_4		
$[\text{Cu}(\text{en})_2]\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Violet)	13.61 (13.59)	9.80 (10.27)	4.25 (4.31)	12.31 (11.98)	53.25 (53.10)	245	1.92
$[\text{Cu}(\text{pn})_2]\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Violet)	13.21 (12.82)	14.35 (14.54)	4.71 (4.88)	12.71 (12.30)	48.12 (47.96)	230	1.99
$[\text{Ni}(\text{en})_3]\text{WO}_4$ (Pink)	12.12 (12.06)	15.15 (14.80)	5.02 (4.96)	17.75 (17.26)	50.75 (50.96)	235	3.06
$[\text{Cu}(\text{pn})_3]\text{WO}_4$ (Pink)	11.08 (11.10)	21.02 (20.41)	6.05 (5.71)	15.33 (15.89)	44.26 (44.39)	240	2.92

ethylenediamine (en) or propylenediamine (pn). The high conductance values show that they are 1 : 1 electrolytes. In the ir spectra, the lowering in the NH stretching frequency suggests that amines are coordinated through their terminal NH_2 groups and the presence of M-N bands around 500 cm^{-1} confirms the same. The magnetic moment and electronic spectral values ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.90$ B.M. and $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 18.00$ kK) suggest a planar structure for the copper(II) complexes, while the nickel(II) complexes are high-spin octahedral as suggested by their μ_{eff}

(except sl. no. 3) exhibit weak diuretic and anti-inflammatory activity, but all of them produce hypotension and also produce well marked effects on histimine, adrenaline and acetylcholine (Table 2).

Experimental

The complexes were obtained by adding amine to copper(II) and nickel(II) tungstate in 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 molar ratios in ethanol and refluxing the solution for 200 h. The distillation of ethanol and cooling the reaction mixture to 0° resulted in the crystallisation

of the complexes which were then dried under reduced pressure over CaCl_2 .

The metals were estimated by standard method¹, WO_4^{2-} was estimated as silver tungstate and C, H and N were analysed microanalytically. Molar conductance was obtained in water ($10^{-3} M$). Ir and electronic spectra were recorded on Perkin-

test compound was administered through a femoral vein and its effect on blood pressure was studied first on normal level and then on pressure response to acetylcholine and histamine⁵.

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TABLE 2—BIOLOGICAL SCREENING DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	LD ₅₀ mg/kg (i.p.)	CNS activity at 1/4 LD ₅₀	Effects on CVS 2.5 mg/kg (i.v.) response to		Histi- mine	Acetyl- choline	DA at 1/4 LD ₅₀	AA at 1/4 LD ₅₀	AIA % inhibi- tion
			B.P.	Adrenaline					
			[Cu(en) ₂]WO ₄ .2H ₂ O	82.50					
[Cu(pn) ₂]WO ₄ .2H ₂ O	80.75	Increased SMA reactivity and response	Hypertension 36 mm/Hg for 15 min	25.0	11.0	13	46	Nil	26.00
[Ni(en) ₃]WO ₄	100.0	Increased SMA analgesia, and response to alaxia, tremor and gasping	Hypotension 20 mm/Hg	37.00	37.00	40	Nil	Present	24.00
[Ni(pn) ₂]WO ₄	92.50	AnaIgesia. max. electroseizure tremor, pilo- erection and straub's tail	Hypotension 15 mm/Hg	80.00	—	16	32	Nil	26.50

*iv = intravenously, ip = intraperitonially, SMA = spontaneous motor activity.

Elmer 621 and Cary 14 spectrophotometers. Magnetic moment was measured by Gouy method.

Biological studies : For CNS effects and acute toxicity studies albino mice weighing 180–200 g were used² and the acute toxic or LD₅₀ dose was determined by administering test compounds intraperitonially and initially observing the mice for 2 h continuously and then at two-hourly intervals for next 6 h. Antiinflammatory and diuretic activity was measured according to the reported technique³ and chlorothiozide (100 mg/kg) was used as standard⁴. For studying cardiovascular effects the tracheae and one major carotid artery of the adult cats anaesthisised with sodium pentobarbitone were cannulated and connected to mareys tambour, the

Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, for biological screening.

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